

Open Access Toolkit for the University of Ottawa

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Introduction

This toolkit provides an overview of open access scholarly publishing for uOttawa researchers and faculty. The toolkit introduces the foundations of open access in the open science movement, surveys the ethical dimensions and challenges faced in the growth of open access, and provides a practical guide to navigating the complexity of the publishing landscape. The toolkit explains the different types of publishing models that enable articles to be published without fees to readers, clarifies funder mandates, and outlines the factors involved in choosing the right type of publication for your research. We hope that the detailed guidance and links to available supports and resources will enable more uOttawa researchers to choose open access publication options.

Why Open Access Matters

Open access (OA) transforms the way knowledge is shared by removing financial and legal barriers to accessing scholarly work. It is rooted in the belief that publicly funded research should be freely available to all.

Societal advancement is made possible through widespread and barrier-free access to cutting-edge research and knowledge, enabling researchers, scholars, clinicians, policymakers, private sector and not-for-profit organizations and the public to use and build on this knowledge.
(Gov't of Canada, 2016)

Peter Suber defines OA as “digital, online, free of charge, and free of most copyright and licensing restrictions” (Suber, 2012, p. 4). This form of “barrier-free access” enables research to reach wider audiences and fosters a more equitable scholarly environment.

Open access is not only about increasing readership but about enhancing the impact, reach, and utility of academic research. Suber argues that “OA benefits authors as well as readers,” noting that “authors want access to readers at least as much as readers want access to authors” (2012, p. 15). The idea that OA is a sacrifice is outdated: in fact, evidence shows that OA articles are cited more often, downloaded more frequently, and contribute more directly to academic careers (p. 16). Open access journals feature the same rigorous peer review processes as journals that publish behind a paywall, and do not inherently differ in quality.

The digital revolution enables this shift. The "access revolution" began when it became possible to make "perfect copies of our work with a worldwide audience at essentially no cost" (Suber, 2012, p. 1). While traditional publishing relies on price and permission barriers, OA replaces these with global access and user freedom. These freedoms are essential to modern research, including activities like text mining, translation, and adaptation to new formats, processes often blocked by restrictive licensing (Suber, 2012, p. 5–6).

Sabina Leonelli builds on this argument by situating OA within the broader movement of Open Science, which seeks to "foster the wide dissemination, scrutiny and reuse of research components for the good of science and society" (Leonelli, 2023, p. 1). She emphasizes that openness must go beyond transparency and data sharing, it should support epistemic diversity and justice, allowing a broader array of knowledge systems and voices to be included in scientific dialogue (2023, p. 1). At uOttawa, [the Open Science Roadmap](#) was created to "develop uOttawa's position as an open science leader and enhance its ability to produce cutting edge and impactful research" (Open Science Working Group, 2024, p. 3).

The Roadmap proposes four pillars:

- 1 Foster a culture of open science at uOttawa;
- 2 Value open science practices;
- 3 Promote and invest in open infrastructure;
- 4 And integrate open science into uOttawa's strategic plan.

Open access publishing is part of each of these pillars of open science practices.

Importantly, OA challenges a business model that has long commodified scholarly knowledge. Suber highlights that scholarly publishing is unique in that authors, editors, and referees are typically not paid, meaning the entire ecosystem can support OA without loss of revenue (2012, p. 9, 17). Scholars write for impact, not income, and they gain rewards through promotion, tenure, citations, and recognition, not royalties (p. 12–13).

Open access also aligns with the missions of universities and funders, which exist to promote knowledge, not profit. As Suber puts it: "Universities and funding agencies pay researchers to make their research into gifts to the public in the widest sense" (2012, p. 14). Therefore, strong OA policies are a natural extension of the values held by academic institutions and research funders.

Finally, OA supports academic freedom and the right to pursue truth without commercial interference. It allows researchers to “focus on what is likely to be true rather than what is likely to sell” (Suber, 2012, p. 12). It supports collaboration, innovation, and inclusive participation in knowledge creation.

In sum, open access matters not only because it breaks down barriers but because it amplifies the core mission of research: to inform, to include, and to impact.

Understanding Open Access

Open access (OA) is not a single method of publishing, but a diverse ecosystem of models that aim to make research freely available to everyone. These models differ in cost, licensing, infrastructure, and who controls publication and dissemination. Understanding the distinctions between them is essential for choosing ethical and effective publication routes.

Gold Open Access

Hybrid Open Access

Green Open Access

Bronze Open Access

Diamond Open Access

Publish-Review-Curate

Gold Open Access

Gold OA refers to articles made openly available directly through the publisher’s website, often upon payment of Article Processing Charges (APCs). According to Peter Suber, gold OA is “delivered by journals, regardless of the journal’s business model” (Suber, 2012, p. 53). These journals typically handle peer review internally and often allow reuse rights through licenses like Creative Commons. Gold OA journals may be offered by commercial publishers, scholarly associations, or not-for-profit organizations.

Gold OA is a common route in biomedicine and offers immediate visibility and legitimacy but can present equity challenges when APCs are prohibitively expensive.

Hybrid Open Access

Hybrid OA allows authors to make individual articles open in otherwise subscription-based journals, typically by paying an APC. Although this option enables publishing in high-impact journals while fulfilling OA mandates, it is controversial due to “double-dipping”, when publishers collect both subscription fees and APCs. Hybrid journals are generally offered by for-profit commercial publishers.

Green Open Access

Green OA, also known as self-archiving, involves depositing a preprint or postprint version of a paper in an institutional or subject-specific repository. Suber explains that “OA repositories... do not perform peer review, although they host and disseminate peer-reviewed articles from elsewhere” (2012, p. 52-53). Green OA repositories are funded by academic or government institutions and disciplinary societies. This route is often cost-free and widely permissible: “A majority of toll-access publishers and journals give blanket permission for author-initiated green OA” (Suber, 2012, p. 54).

However, most green OA is “gratis OA”, free to read but lacking reuse rights (Piwowar et al., 2018, p. 3). Still, it is the most flexible and scalable model, especially in disciplines like physics where repositories like arXiv dominate. The Recherche uO Research (RUOR) repository provides green OA hosting for all uOttawa-affiliated researchers.

Bronze Open Access

Bronze OA is a more ambiguous form where articles are free to read on the publisher’s website but lack explicit reuse licenses. These are often promotional or temporarily available articles, and Piwowar et al. found bronze to be

“the most common OA subtype” in their study (2018, p. 1, 5). However, the absence of clear licensing means that users often cannot legally reuse or redistribute content.

Diamond Open Access

Diamond OA journals charge neither readers nor authors and are usually supported by institutions, libraries, or consortia, and often rely on volunteer academic labor (Corker et al., 2024, p. 5). While this model promotes equity and avoids the APC barrier, sustainability can be challenging. In Canada, there has been significant investment in community- and academic-led diamond OA infrastructure from the Canada Foundation for Innovation, coordinated by Coalition Publica, fostering growth in the availability of cost-free publication and dissemination of Canadian research.

Some PRC platforms (e.g., PREREview, Peer Community In) also operate under the diamond OA model, showing that this business model can apply across various forms of OA infrastructure.

Emerging Model: Publish-Review-Curate (PRC)

The publish-review-curate (PRC) model is an emerging, modular approach to scholarly communication. Instead of combining publishing, peer review, and editorial curation into one centralized process (as in traditional journals), PRC separates these into distinct, open stages:

“In the publish stage, a research artifact... is made public by a researcher. In the review stage, reviewers transparently evaluate the research artifact... In the curate stage, research artifacts are compiled into collections” (Corker et al., 2024, p. 1).

This model supports decentralization and flexibility. Publishing occurs via preprint servers or repositories; reviewing is done by independent review platforms (like eLife or Peer Community In); and curation involves highlighting, summarizing, or endorsing research in topical collections.

A key benefit of PRC is author control and transparency: “Control of whether and when to publish is with authors in the PRC model, whereas in the traditional model it lies with a journal” (Corker et al., 2024, p. 4). It also encourages reuse and discoverability through rich metadata, persistent identifiers, and open licensing.

Overlay journals, such as those built on arXiv or bioRxiv, represent one application of the PRC model. These journals “provide review and curation services for articles that have already been published,” further demonstrating the model’s flexibility (Corker et al., 2024, p. 5).

See Practical Guidelines for Faculty and Researchers for more information on choosing an OA model for your research.

Ethical Considerations

The Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), a membership organization that promotes ethical practices in scholarly publishing, outlines key criteria in its [Principles of Transparency and Best Practice in Scholarly Publishing](#). These criteria apply equally to paywalled and open access publications, and include ensuring that journal names are unique and that websites are well-supported, regularly maintained, and secure. Additionally, the publishing schedule must be clearly stated and strictly followed.

Archiving is also crucial, as journals should have a plan for electronic backup and long-term digital preservation. Furthermore, the publisher’s copyright policy should be clearly stated for the website and its content. Content designated as open access must be distributed under an open license.

Editors and publishers are responsible for maintaining the integrity of scholarly literature by clearly outlining policies and procedures for handling research misconduct, including plagiarism, citation manipulation, and data falsification. Journal policies and editorial statements must not encourage or permit such misconduct. If allegations arise regarding a submitted or published article, editors and publishers should follow COPE's guidance (or an equivalent standard) to address them appropriately.

The peer review process and participants should be clearly stated on the website. In terms of ownership and management, organizational names should not be used in a way that could mislead potential authors and editors about the nature of the journal's owner. Journals should have editorial boards or other advisory bodies whose members are recognized experts in the subject areas stated in the journal's aims and scope. Journals should also provide the full names and affiliations of their editors, as well as contact information for the editorial office, including a full mailing address, on the journal's website.

In "The Academic Ethics of Open Access to Research and Scholarship," Willinsky highlights several critical ethical considerations particular to OA publishing. Willinsky raises the issue of predatory journals, which exploit the OA model by charging high publication fees without providing

providing legitimate peer review or editorial oversight. The paper also emphasizes the importance of research integrity and transparency, asserting that OA publishing must adhere to ethical standards by ensuring data and findings are accurately and fairly represented, with clear policies on peer review, authorship, and conflict of interest. Additionally, it discusses the financial barriers associated with OA, particularly the challenges posed by Article Processing Charges (APCs), which can prevent authors from low-resource institutions from accessing or publishing research.

Challenges in the Context of Open Access

Business models based on APCs and subscriptions are highly inequitable. While APCs were initially seen as a solution to subscription paywalls, they create new inequities, excluding authors from certain career stages, genders, institutions, and regions (Kiley, 2021). This raises concerns that transitioning to open access may simply replace one form of inequity with another. Kiley (2021) highlights that in the effort to transition research articles to open access, significant attention and funding were directed toward encouraging existing subscription-based and primarily commercially published journals to adopt OA options and eventually shift to OA.

While this strategy was logical, given that many researchers continued to publish in subscription or mixed-model journals, it likely delayed the widespread adoption of fully OA journals and emerging, scholar-led models, such as pre-printing and publishing platforms that support post-publication peer review.

Finally, Kiley points out that researchers continued to believe that their future success depended upon having an article published in a high impact factor journal resulted in some researchers not fully complying with OA policies (See Research Assessment). This non-compliance was in part due to high-impact factor journals being slow to adopt OA-compliant publishing policies.

Open Access in the Francophone Context

UNESCO's Recommendations on Open Science emphasize the importance of multilingual scientific knowledge. Other initiatives, such as the Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism, OPERAS, and COARA, advocate for the protection of local languages and the promotion of research dissemination in diverse linguistic contexts.

In Canada, Érudit, a leading publishing platform, is the largest provider of Canadian French and bilingual research publications in the humanities and social sciences.

Érudit hosts and disseminates more than three hundred scholarly journals, most open access. In the same context, Coalition Publica, led by Érudit and the Public Knowledge Project (PKP), supports open access, open science, and the development of open-source software while promoting the publication of research in French.

Additionally, Les Classiques des sciences sociales, a well-known digital library, provides free access to a vast collection of French-language works in the social sciences, making valuable scholarly knowledge widely accessible.

Funder Mandates

If you, or your collaborators, receive government funding for your research, you must make your resulting publications available open access. Following the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021) and Canada's Roadmap for Open Science (Gov't of Canada, 2020), many research funding organizations in Canada and around the world have adopted mandates requiring the results of research funded by public funds be published without paywall barriers.

These mandates apply to the results of all research that is funded by the federal Canadian granting agencies – the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR), Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of

Funder mandates at a glance

	Tri-Agencies 2015-2025	Tri-Agencies 2026- (Draft)	FRQ	Plan S (FRQ 2023-)
Open Access when?	Within 12 months of publication	Immediately upon publication	Within 12 months of publication	Immediately upon publication
What routes for OA are acceptable?	Green, Gold, Hybrid, Diamond	Deposit in institutional repository mandatory (Green), in addition to other routes as desired	Green, Gold, Hybrid, Diamond	Green, Gold, Diamond
Copyright retention	Recommended	Mandatory		Mandatory
Open licensing (e.g. Creative Commons)	Recommended	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory
What version of the article should be OA?	Any version after peer review	Author-accepted manuscript (AAM) or Version of Record (VoR) - If necessary, a preprint, marked as unrefereed version	Final Peer-Reviewed Manuscript	AAM or VoR
Are publishing fees eligible grant expenses?	Yes	Yes	No	Yes, for Gold OA journals (not Hybrid)
Applicable to graduate students and fellowships?	No, but encouraged	No, but no-cost options are encouraged	No	No

Canada (NSERC), and the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada (SSHRC), known together as the Tri-Agencies – as well as the Fonds de Recherche du Québec (FRQ). The Tri-Agency open access policy on publications (TAOAPP 2015) is currently under revision, with the new policy coming into effect for all research grants beginning in 2026.

A draft of the changes expected was released on 13 Mar 2025, with the terms summarized in the chart above.

In Canada, these policies do not require you to publish in an open access journal (gold route), because the deposit of a paper published in a subscription journal in an open access repository (green route) is also acceptable.

Beginning in 2026, this deposit will be required immediately upon publication, regardless of where the article is published.

Compliance strategies for researchers

Researchers should make themselves familiar with the policies in place for all funders (for all collaborators) and determine if open access publication is required before submitting to a journal. Normally, the policy for the corresponding author takes precedence.

Mandatory deposit

Beginning in 2026, deposit in institutional repositories (such as uO Research) of all peer-reviewed publications arising from research that has received public funding will be required (Govt of Canada, 2025b), whether the research is published in an open access journal or behind a paywall. It is the responsibility of the author to ensure that the publisher's policy will permit this deposit, and we recommend that you make your mandatory deposit funder requirement clear when submitting for publication. (See Practical Guidelines for more information)

Copyright retention

To facilitate deposit, authors must retain copyright over their work and not transfer it to the publisher. The agencies will supply rights retention text for you to insert into the

publishing agreement (e.g. Gov't of Canada, 2025a, 24). This ensures that you have the legal right to control where your work gets deposited and republished.

Open licensing

When you retain the copyright to your work, you need to specify the terms under which others can read and use the work (licensing). A Creative Commons BY (CC-BY) license is the preferred (and sometimes required) option, which allows the sharing, archiving, and adaptation of your work, but requires attribution. For example, a CC-BY license would permit another scholar to produce a translation of your work into a local language, while maintaining the attribution of authorship to you, while this use would not be permitted by traditional publishers.

Article version

Some publishers will permit the deposit of the final published article in a repository, or if the article is published open access (gold or diamond), this version of record (VoR) can be deposited. This is the best option, since the final changes, page numbers, and images will be consistent for all users of your work. Many paywalled publishers will not permit this version to be used, so instead you would deposit the author approved manuscript (AAM), which is the author's last version of the article, including any changes made after peer review.

The layout and page numbers will not reflect the published version. In the rare cases where the publisher refuses to permit deposit of even the author approved manuscript, a preprint (version prior to peer review) will fulfill the open access deposit requirement for the Tri-Agencies, provided it is marked as an “unrefereed version” (Gov’t of Canada, 2025b).

Eligible fees

Gold and hybrid open access publications are often funded by fees paid by the article authors, known as article processing charges (APCs). These fees are eligible grant expenses for Tri-Agency grant recipients. For FRQ grant recipients, as of 2023 fees for publishing in hybrid journals are not eligible, but those for fully OA journals are eligible. Fees may also be waived, particularly if the library has an agreement with the publisher (See Financial Support for more information).

Find out more:

<https://science.gc.ca/site/science/en/interagency-research-funding/policies-and-guidelines/open-access/frequently-asked-questions>

Support for Open Access at uOttawa

Supporting Researchers Who Practice Open Access

The uOttawa library provides [support for researchers](#) who wish to publish open access.

We offer:

- Recherche uO Research (RUOR) – our institutional repository, managed by the library
- Practical guidance in selecting open access journals (See also Practical Guidelines, below)
- Detailed web guidance about finding open access content, avoiding deceptive publishers, and navigating funder requirements (University of Ottawa, n.d. a)
- Guidance on copyright and licensing from the [copyright office](#)
- Direct support on practices within your discipline from your liaison librarian and the scholarly communications librarian

Financial Support for Publishing Open Access Research

Through the collective negotiation of the Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN), uO library has agreements in place to provide discounts or waivers of the fees for open access publishing from many commercial publishers. These agreements require a substantial budgetary investment from the library. Consult the [website](#) to find the current list of publishers and terms.

All faculty members, staff, current graduate students, postdoctoral fellows, adjunct professors, and researchers working for University of Ottawa research centres and affiliated research institutes are eligible to publish under these agreements.

The library does not provide direct financial support to cover APCs, having redirected funds that previously supported these fees to the above agreements, and to support more equitable and sustainable options for open access publishing (diamond, green, and publish-review-curate models). APCs may be eligible expenses for your grant funder, or you may be able to access financial support from your department or discipline.

Alternatively, consider choosing a diamond open access journal that does not charge author fees (See Publishing in a Diamond, Gold, or Hybrid Journal).

Open Access Publishing Services at uOttawa

The library provides [hosting and publishing services](#) for uOttawa-affiliated journals on the Open Journal Systems (OJS) platform. OJS was created in Canada by the Public Knowledge Project (PKP) and is used by more than 50,000 journals around the world. We offer training, technical support, and workflow optimization for OJS, as well as advice and expertise on making your journal discoverable in indexes like DOAJ and Scholars Portal.

Practical support for integrating features like ORCID and assigning DOIs help uOttawa journals become effective and successful digital publications. We also offer hosting and support for open educational resources, course journals, and student journals.

University of Ottawa Press publishes high quality scholarly books and ebooks. The uO Library provides financial support to publish four new open access books per year, two in English, and two in French. University of Ottawa Press has thus far made 87 scholarly books available open access. See their [web site](#) for their policy and list of titles.

Practical Guidelines

Green Open Access

Recherche uO Research (RUOR) is uOttawa's institutional open access repository, managed by the library. The benefits of depositing in uO Research include increased visibility online, usage statistics, and permanent URLs and DOIs so that your work can always be located (University of Ottawa, n.d. b), in addition to the other benefits of open access for your work (See Why Open Access Matters).

Depositing either published or unpublished work is a quick and easy process but taking special care with the description and metadata fields will help to make your work easier to find for your readers. Before depositing, you will need to verify your journal's policy on which version is permitted using the JISC Open Policy Finder (formerly Sherpa/Romeo). You may also wish to deposit in a subject or disciplinary repository, such as PubMedCentral, depending on the practices in your field.

Publishing in a Diamond, Gold, or Hybrid Journal

Open access publication is the best way to ensure the widest possible access to your research. A wide variety of practices and funding models support this free reader access, including some which rely on fees from authors (APCs). Individual journals may be run by commercial for-profit publishers, scholarly associations, academic institutions, or not-for-profit organizations.

When considering publishing open access, you should consult the [Directory of Open Access Journals](#) (DOAJ) for information about fully open access journals in your discipline. Select "Journals without Fees" below the search bar to see options without fees for the author. The DOAJ has stringent criteria to be included, and listed journals have been vetted for ethical publishing

ethical publishing practices, but there are legitimate open access journals that are not listed, especially if they are newly launched. The [Érudit platform](#) disseminates more than two hundred Canadian open access journals, mostly in French, but some in English as well. CRKN provides a [list of open access journals](#) that are supported by Canadian academic libraries and not listed in Érudit or DOAJ. If a journal you are considering is not listed in one of these lists, consult your academic liaison librarian to confirm that is an appropriate venue.

Some subscription journals offer the option to publish individual articles openly (hybrid OA). APCs will normally fund this option, which are often much higher than those for fully open access journals. It is important to note that funders that have signed onto Plan S, such as FRQ, do not support this type of publication and will not fund the APCs (Birsan, 2021). However, many hybrid journals are offered by publishers that uO library has agreements with to partially or fully waive the fees (See Financial Support).

Avoiding Deceptive Publishers

The author-pays model of funding open access publishing through APCs and other fees, combined with the pressures of publish-or-perish academic culture, have opened a space for the unscrupulous to exploit scholarly publishing for financial gain

without delivering the services promised. Often called predatory publishers, they provide cursory or no peer review or editorial oversight, charge hidden or unexpectedly large fees, publish deceptive information about impact factors or indexing, solicit scholars to review work outside their area of expertise, or otherwise diverge from ethical publishing practices (See Ethical Considerations).

The web tool [Think, Check, Submit](#) provides a checklist for avoiding the traps of such scams. Researchers can protect themselves by verifying that the information on a journal website corresponds with what is found in the appropriate databases, and any fees are clearly communicated. Read selected articles from the journal to evaluate if their quality meets your expectations. The [uO library website](#) offers further guidance for evaluating a prospective journal. Contact your liaison librarian for more help with vetting a journal's practices.

Research Assessment and Open Access

The use of quantitative indicators such as the Journal Impact Factor, Field Weighted Citation Impact, or H-index in assessing the output of individual scholars is a problematic practice because the citation distributions for journals are highly skewed, publication practices vary for different fields, the indicators can be manipulated by editorial policies,

and the data used to collect and calculate them are not transparent (DORA, n.d.). Nevertheless, these numbers are still widely used in the assessment of research outputs for funding and promotion.

More than 26,000 individuals and organizations (including each of the Tri-Agencies, FRQ, the uO Institute of Mental Health Research at the Royal, and the School of Epidemiology and Public Health) have signed on to the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) to reform research assessment practices, including the elimination of the use of these indicators in assessing individual researchers. The indicators were developed and intended to help libraries determine which journals are of more value to their patrons, not for assessing researchers. Because these indicators are calculated by for-profit commercial publishers, such as Clarivate and Elsevier, diamond and gold OA journals from independent publishers and scholarly associations are not well represented in their calculations.

If these practices persist in your field and your career is at an early stage, publishing at least once in a journal with a higher impact factor score might be a consideration to balance against the higher actual citation rates of open access research. This may mean publishing behind a paywall, or open access may be possible in a journal covered by a publication

agreement (See Financial Support). If your department or field relies on these metrics for research assessment, you may also wish to direct your Chair to the DORA Reformscape guidance on responsible research assessment for your discipline (DORA, n.d.).

Factors When Choosing a Right Journal

- Does your funder mandate open access? For example, if you receive funding from SSHRC, NSERC, CIHR, FRQ, or many private funders, you may be required to ensure that the results of your research are freely accessible.
- Is the journal respected and widely read in your field? Have you read and cited articles from this journal in your work? Have colleagues cited or published there?
- Does uO library have an agreement with the journal's publisher providing a waiver or discount of author fees?
- Is your research of special interest to French-Canadians? If so, consider publishing in French in a journal hosted by Érudit. If you publish in English, a CC-BY license will make translation of your work by others permissible.
- Is it important to you that your research results be immediately available to policy makers and other non-academic readers? If so, open access publication will facilitate this use.
- How quickly do you want other researchers to have access to your results? If speed is of the essence, consider the publish-review-curate model, where a preprint is posted, then peer review is conducted openly.
- Are there incentives in your field or department recognizing distinguished contributions to open science that your work would be ineligible for if you published in a paywalled journal?
- Do your department's research assessment practices rely on quantitative indicators, such as the Impact Factor, Field Weighted Citation Impact, or H-Index?
- Do you have access to funding to cover APCs?
- Consult with your liaison librarian for more guidance

Resource Guide

[Think, check, submit](#) - checklist tool for evaluating a journal before submitting for publication.

[Directory of Open Access Journals](#) (DOAJ) - an index of global open access journals, vetted for publishing ethics. Managed by an independent non-profit foundation.

[Jisc Open Policy Finder](#) (Formerly known as Sherpa-Romeo) - search tool for finding publisher policies on depositing work into repositories for green OA. Jisc is a not-for-profit organisation supporting UK education and research.

[Canadian Research Knowledge Network](#) (CRKN - RCDR) - Consortium of 89 research libraries across Canada. Provides collective negotiation of agreements with publishers. Open access tab has a search tool for finding open access publishing options covered by agreements.

[Committee on Publication Ethics](#) (COPE) - Organisation providing guidance on ethical practices in scholarly publishing. Created the [Principles of Transparency and Best Practice in Scholarly Publishing](#).

[Érudit](#) - Quebec-based dissemination platform for primarily French language open access research, especially in the Arts, Social Sciences, and Humanities. Includes journals, books, theses, and reports.

[Coalition Publica](#) - Partnership between Érudit and Public Knowledge Project to support open access infrastructure in Canada. Hosts archives of Canadian journals, newspapers, and magazines. Conducts bibliometric research and supplies data.

[Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association](#) (OASPA) - Large association of organizations who publish open access research.

Sets policies and collects resources and links.

[GoTriple](#) - a multi-language discovery platform and aggregator for open access publications the social sciences and humanities. Funded by the European Commission. Supports eleven languages.

Conclusion

Choosing a journal to publish your research is a decision that will reward careful consideration because the landscape of scholarly publishing is diverse and complex. The growth of open access publishing platforms has made it possible for a much wider range of readers to access the results of research without subscriptions. Open access publication enhances the impact, reach, and utility of academic research, and it aligns with the core values of researchers and academic institutions to foster innovation and build knowledge for the common good. There are many routes to making your work available open access explored in this toolkit, each with their own advantages and disadvantages, and different publication practices inform the academic culture of different disciplines. The uOttawa library is here to support its researchers in navigating this complex terrain.

Resources

- Birsan, G. (2021, June 1). *Les Fonds de recherche du Québec appuient la science ouverte en joignant la cOAlition S*. Fonds de recherche du Québec. <https://frq.gouv.qc.ca/les-fonds-de-recherche-du-quebec-appuient-la-science-ouverte-en-joignant-la-coalition-s/>
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